

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5692863>

ZENODO, 16(11): 5–59

[DOI:10.5281/zenodo.5692863](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5692863)

Received: October 29, 2021

Accepted: November 13, 2021, 2021

Published: November 13, 2021, 2021

Research article

Classical logic and study design

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Abstract:

Background:

The scientific value of a study is determined by various factors, but to a major extent by the design of a study too.

Methods:

Ex post, it is difficult to correct errors in study design completely. Therefore, various mathematical aspects of a design of a study are discussed in this article.

Results:

Under conditions of causal investigations, it is appropriate to assure a study design with $p(\text{IOI}) = 0$. The relative risk and the odds ratio are not for sure logically consistent.

Conclusion:

A study of causal relationships properly planned should comply with $p(\text{IOI}) = 0$ as much as possible.

Keywords: Study design; Bias; Cause; Effect; Causal relationship k

1. Introduction

Science doesn't have an easy job in order to replace human experience and human intuition completely, and doesn't have to. Scientific knowledge is one source of hope for the men of this time, and potentially of very great benefit to mankind. However, the misery (Dominiczak, 2004) of science of which scientist have been made ministers is really big, science or scientist (Gianicolo et al., 2020) can be the cause of massive harm (Jordan, 2016) too. So every one of us and every day again has to deal with both sides of the same coin simultaneously. Despite all the adverse circumstances, we have just as good a right to ask whether it is permissible to rely on (claimed) scientific knowledge and to what extent? No wonder that most of us seem to be caught up by our firm belief that knowledge gained

from large studies is more reliable than knowledge obtained from smaller studies. However, is such an attitude always and without any exception fully appropriate? It should be considered that a variety of biases in the era of big data are known (sampling error, measurement error, et cetera) too. Consequently, despite the presumed benefits of big studies, a large sample size has theoretically the potential to magnify the bias associated with an error resulting from sampling or from study design et cetera. Especially, a study based on a very large sample size which is not representative of the population can be of relatively little value. To learn from history, there is documented evidence that studies with more than 2.4 million people have gone so wrong (Kaplan et al., 2014). It is therefore perfectly satisfactory, if, among other things, the greatest possible attention is paid to the design of a study.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Study design and quality of data

The quality of the data (Barukčić, 2019a,b) of each study included was assessed separately by the index of unfairness or the index of independence. A study design should be fair and representative as much as possible in order to assure data, which we can rely on and work with. The index of unfairness (Barukčić, 2019a) and the index of independence (Barukčić, 2019b) are indicating to which extent data could be biased due to study design. Under ideal conditions, it is desirable that $p(\text{IOU}) = 0$ or $p(\text{IOI}) = 0$ or that even $p(\text{IOU}) = p(\text{IOI}) = 0$.

Table 1. The quality of data (see Barukčić, 2019a, p. 25)

p(IOU)	Quality of study design
$0 < p(\text{IOU}) \leq 0,25$	Unfair study design
$0,25 < p(\text{IOU}) \leq 0,5$	Very unfair study design
$0,5 < p(\text{IOU}) \leq 0,75$	Highly unfair study design
$0,75 < p(\text{IOU}) \leq 1,0$	Extremely unfair study design

2.2. Methods

The nature of definitions is discussed by scientist since ancient times. Many times, several different kinds of definitions are necessary to solve a scientific issue properly. Even if often in play, inappropriate definitions can lead to logical fallacies too.

2.2.1. The number +0

Definition 2.1 (The number +0). Let i denote the imaginary number (Bombelli, 1579). The imaginary number i is known to be defined solely by the property that its square is -1 . According to today valid rules of algebra, the number +0 is defined as the expression

$$+0 \equiv +1 \times +0 \equiv +0 \times +1 \equiv +1 - 1 \equiv +1 + i^2 \equiv +1 + e^{i\pi} \equiv -(+1) \quad (2.1)$$

while '=' or \equiv denotes the equals sign (Recorde, 1557) or equality sign (Rolle, 1690) used to indicate equality and '-' (Widmann, 1489; Pacioli, 1494) denotes minus signs used to represent the operations of subtraction and the notions of negative as well and '+' denotes the plus (Recorde, 1557) signs used to represent the operations of addition and the notions of positive as well. Negation is denoted by \neg .

Remark 2.1. Roger Cotes (1682 – 1716) ([Cotes and Halley, 1714](#)) or Leonhard Euler's (1707 – 1783) identity ([Euler, 1748](#)) is regarded as one of the most beautiful equations ([Wilson, 2018](#)). In this context, it is provisionally presumed, that Euler's identity ([Euler, 1748](#)) is logically sound and correct.

2.2.2. The number +1

Definition 2.2 (The number +1). According to today valid rules of algebra, the number +1 is defined as the expression

$$+1 \equiv +1 + 0 \equiv +1 - 0 \equiv \neg(+0) \quad (2.2)$$

while again '=' or \equiv may denote the equals sign ([Recorde, 1557](#)) or equality sign ([Rolle, 1690](#)) used to indicate equality and '-' ([Widmann, 1489](#); [Pacioli, 1494](#)) denotes minus signs used to represent the operations of subtraction and the notions of negative as well and '+' denotes the plus ([Recorde, 1557](#)) signs used to represent the operations of addition and the notions of positive as well.

2.2.3. Single event distribution

Let a **random variable** ([Gosset, 1914](#)) X denote something like a function defined on a probability space, which itself maps from the sample space ([Neyman and Pearson, 1933](#)) to the real numbers. A single event distribution is more or less a discrete probability distribution of any random variable X which takes a certain (observer independent) single value X_t at a **Bernoulli trial** ([Uspensky, 1937](#), p. 45) (period of time) t with the probability $p(X_t)$. The same random variable X takes a certain single anti value \underline{X}_t at a Bernoulli trial (period of time) t with the probability $1-p(X_t)$. There are conditions in nature where a random variable X can take only the values either +0 or +1. Under these conditions the random variable X takes the value 1 with probability $p(X_t = +1)$ and the value 0 with probability $q(X_t = +0) = 1 - p(X_t = +1)$ while the single event distribution passes over into the **Bernoulli distribution**, named after Swiss mathematician Jacob Bernoulli ([Bernoulli, 1713](#)). Less formally, many times, the Bernoulli distribution is represented by a (possibly not biased) coin toss where 1 and 0 would represent 'heads' and 'tails' (or vice versa), respectively. However, the relationship between random variables ([Gosset, 1914](#)) can be investigated by many ([Gosset, 1908](#)) methods, including the tools of probability theory, too.

Definition 2.3 (Two by two table of single event random variables).

The two by two or contingency table which has been introduced by Karl Pearson ([Pearson, 1904](#)) in 1904 harbours still a large variety of topics and debates. Central to this is the problem to apply the laws of classical logic on data sets, which concerns the justification of inferences which extrapolate from sample data to general facts. Nevertheless, a contingency table is still an appropriate theoretical model too for studying the relationships between random variables, including *Bernoulli* ([Bernoulli, 1713](#)) (*i.e. +0/+1*) distributed random variables existing or occurring at the same *Bernoulli trial* ([Uspensky, 1937](#)) (period of time) t .

In this context, let a random variable A at the *Bernoulli trial* ([Uspensky, 1937](#)) (period of time) t , denoted by A_t , indicate a risk factor, a condition, a cause et cetera and occur or exist with the probability $p(A_t)$ at the *Bernoulli trial* ([Uspensky, 1937](#)) (period of time) t . Let $E(A_t)$ denote the expectation value of A_t . In general it is

$$p(A_t) \equiv p(a_t) + p(b_t) \quad (2.3)$$

The expectation value $E(A_t)$ follows as

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(A_t) &\equiv A_t \times p(A_t) \\
 &\equiv A_t \times (p(a_t) + p(b_t)) \\
 &\equiv (A_t \times p(a_t)) + (A_t \times p(b_t)) \\
 &\equiv E(a_t) + E(b_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.4}$$

Under conditions of +0/+1 distributed Bernoulli random variables it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(A_t) &\equiv A_t \times p(A_t) \\
 &\equiv (+0 + 1) \times p(A_t) \\
 &\equiv p(A_t) \\
 &\equiv p(a_t) + p(b_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.5}$$

Furthermore, it is

$$p(\underline{A}_t) \equiv p(c_t) + p(d_t) \equiv (1 - p(A_t)) \tag{2.6}$$

The expectation value $E(\underline{A}_t)$ is given as

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(\underline{A}_t) &\equiv A_t \times (1 - p(A_t)) \\
 &\equiv A_t \times (p(c_t) + p(d_t)) \\
 &\equiv (A_t \times p(c_t)) + (A_t \times p(d_t)) \\
 &\equiv E(c_t) + E(d_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.7}$$

Under conditions of +0/+1 distributed Bernoulli random variables we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(\underline{A}_t) &\equiv A_t \times (1 - p(A_t)) \\
 &\equiv (+0 + 1) \times (1 - p(A_t)) \\
 &\equiv (1 - p(A_t)) \\
 &\equiv p(c_t) + p(d_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.8}$$

Let a random variable B at the *Bernoulli trial* (Uspensky, 1937) (period of time) t , denoted by B_t , indicate an outcome, a conditioned, an effect et cetera and occur or exist with the probability $p(B_t)$ at the *Bernoulli trial* (Uspensky, 1937) (period of time) t . Let $E(B_t)$ denote the expectation value of B_t . In general it is

$$p(B_t) \equiv p(a_t) + p(c_t) \tag{2.9}$$

The expectation value $E(B_t)$ is given by the equation

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(B_t) &\equiv B_t \times p(B_t) \\
 &\equiv B_t \times (p(a_t) + p(c_t)) \\
 &\equiv (B_t \times p(a_t)) + (B_t \times p(c_t)) \\
 &\equiv E(a_t) + E(c_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.10}$$

Under conditions of +0/+1 distributed Bernoulli random variables it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(B_t) &\equiv B_t \times p(B_t) \\
 &\equiv (+0 + 1) \times p(B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(a_t) + p(c_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.11}$$

Furthermore, it is

$$p(\underline{B}_t) \equiv p(b_t) + p(d_t) \equiv (1 - p(B_t)) \tag{2.12}$$

The expectation value $E(\underline{B}_t)$ is given by the equation

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(\underline{B}_t) &\equiv B_t \times (1 - p(B_t)) \\
 &\equiv B_t \times (p(b_t) + p(d_t)) \\
 &\equiv (B_t \times p(b_t)) + (B_t \times p(d_t)) \\
 &\equiv E(b_t) + E(d_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.13}$$

Under conditions of +0/+1 distributed Bernoulli random variables it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(\underline{B}_t) &\equiv B_t \times (1 - p(B_t)) \\
 &\equiv (+0 + 1) \times (1 - p(B_t)) \\
 &\equiv (1 - p(B_t)) \\
 &\equiv p(b_t) + p(d_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.14}$$

Let $p(a_t) = p(A_t \wedge B_t)$ denote the joint probability distribution of A_t and B_t at the same Bernoulli trial (period of time) t . In general, it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(a_t) &\equiv E(A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv (A_t \times B_t) \times p(A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv (A_t \times B_t) \times p(a_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.15}$$

Under conditions of +0/+1 distributed Bernoulli random variables, it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(a_t) &\equiv E(A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv (A_t \times B_t) \times p(A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv ((+0 + 1) \times (+0 + 1)) \times p(A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(a_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.16}$$

Let $p(b_t) = p(A_t \wedge \neg B_t)$ denote the joint probability distribution of A_t and not B_t at the same Bernoulli trial (period of time) t . In general, it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(b_t) &\equiv E(A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv (A_t \times \neg B_t) \times p(A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv (A_t \times \neg B_t) \times p(b_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.17}$$

Under conditions of +0/+1 distributed Bernoulli random variables, it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(b_t) &\equiv E(A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv (A_t \times \neg B_t) \times p(A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv ((+0 + 1) \times (+0 + 1)) \times p(A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(b_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.18}$$

Let $p(c_t) = p(\neg A_t \wedge B_t)$ denote the joint probability distribution of not A_t and B_t at the same Bernoulli trial (period of time) t . In general, it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(c_t) &\equiv E(\neg A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv (\neg A_t \wedge B_t) \times p(\neg A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv (\neg A_t \wedge B_t) \times p(c_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.19}$$

Under conditions of +0/+1 distributed Bernoulli random variables, it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(c_t) &\equiv E(\neg A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv (\neg A_t \times B_t) \times p(\neg A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv ((+0 + 1) \times (+0 + 1)) \times p(\neg A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(\neg A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(c_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.20}$$

Let $p(d_t) = p(\neg A_t \wedge \neg B_t)$ denote the joint probability distribution of not A_t and not B_t at the same Bernoulli trial (period of time) t . In general, it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(d_t) &\equiv E(\neg A_t \times \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv (\neg A_t \times \neg B_t) \times p(\neg A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv (\neg A_t \times \neg B_t) \times p(d_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.21}$$

Under conditions of +0/+1 distributed Bernoulli random variables, it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(d_t) &\equiv E(\neg A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv (\neg A_t \times \neg B_t) \times p(\neg A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv ((+0 + 1) \times (+0 + 1)) \times p(\neg A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(\neg A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(d_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.22}$$

In general, it is

$$p(a_t) + p(b_t) + p(c_t) + p(d_t) \equiv +1 \tag{2.23}$$

Table 2 provide us with an overview of the definitions above.

Table 2. The two by two table of Bernoulli random variables

		Conditioned B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition	TRUE	$p(a_t)$	$p(b_t)$	$p(A_t)$
	A_t	FALSE	$p(c_t)$	$p(\underline{A}_t)$
		$p(B_t)$	$p(\underline{B}_t)$	+1

2.2.4. Binomial random variables

Definition 2.4 (Two by two table of Binomial random variables).

Let $a, b, c, d, A, \underline{A}, B,$ and \underline{B} denote expectation values. Under conditions where *the probability of an event, an outcome, a success et cetera is constant from Bernoulli trial to Bernoulli trial t* , it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 A &= N \times E(A_t) \\
 &\equiv N \times (A_t \times p(A_t)) \\
 &\equiv N \times (p(A_t) + p(B_t)) \\
 &\equiv N \times p(A_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.24}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
 B &= N \times E(B_t) \\
 &\equiv N \times (B_t \times p(B_t)) \\
 &\equiv N \times (p(A_t) + p(c_t)) \\
 &\equiv N \times p(B_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.25}$$

where N might denote the population or even the sample size. Furthermore, it is

$$a \equiv N \times (E(A_t)) \equiv N \times (p(A_t)) \tag{2.26}$$

and

$$b \equiv N \times (E(B_t)) \equiv N \times (p(B_t)) \tag{2.27}$$

and

$$c \equiv N \times (E(c_t)) \equiv N \times (p(c_t)) \tag{2.28}$$

and

$$d \equiv N \times (E(d_t)) \equiv N \times (p(d_t)) \tag{2.29}$$

and

$$a + b + c + d \equiv A + \underline{A} \equiv B + \underline{B} \equiv N \tag{2.30}$$

Table 3 provide us again an overview of a two by two table of Binomial random variables.

Table 3. The two by two table of Binomial random variables

		Conditioned B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition A_t	TRUE	a	b	A
	FALSE	c	d	<u>A</u>
		B	<u>B</u>	N

2.2.5. Independence

Definition 2.5 (Independence).

In general, an event A_t at the Bernoulli trial t need not but can be independent of the existence or of the occurrence of another event B_t at the same Bernoulli trial t . Mathematically, independence (Moivre, 1718; Kolmogoroff, 1933) in terms of probability theory is defined at the same (period of) time t (i.e. Bernoulli trial t) as

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(A_t \wedge B_t) &\equiv p(A_t) \times p(B_t) \\
 &\equiv \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N (A_t \wedge B_t)}{N} \equiv \frac{N \times (p(a_t))}{N} \equiv 1 - p(A_t | B_t) \equiv 1 - p(A_t \uparrow B_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.31}$$

2.2.6. Dependence

Definition 2.6 (Dependence).

The dependence of events (Barukčić, 1989, p. 57-61) is defined as

$$p\left(\underbrace{A_t \wedge B_t \wedge C_t \wedge \dots}_n\right) \equiv \sqrt[n]{\underbrace{p(A_t) \times p(B_t) \times p(C_t) \times \dots}_n} \tag{2.32}$$

2.2.7. Exclusion relationship

Definition 2.7 (Exclusion relationship [EXCL]).

Mathematically, the exclusion (EXCL) relationship, denoted by $p(A_t | B_t)$ in terms of statistics and

probability theory, is defined (Barukčić, 1989, p. 68-70) as

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(A_t | B_t) &\equiv p(A_t \uparrow B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(b_t) + p(c_t) + p(d_t) \\
 &\equiv \frac{N \times (p(b_t) + p(c_t) + p(d_t))}{N} \\
 &\equiv \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N (A_t \vee B_t)}{N} \equiv \frac{b + c + d}{N} \\
 &\equiv \frac{b + A}{N} \\
 &\equiv \frac{c + B}{N} \\
 &\equiv +1
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.33}$$

Based on the 1913 Henry Maurice Sheffer (1882-1964) relationship, the Sheffer stroke (Sheffer, 1913; Nicod, 1917) usually denoted by \uparrow , it is $p(A_t \wedge B_t) \equiv 1 - p(A_t | B_t)$ (see table 4).

Table 4. A_t excludes B_t and vice versa.

		Conditioned (COVID-19) B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition (Vaccine)	TRUE	+0	$p(b_t)$	$p(A_t)$
	FALSE	$p(c_t)$	$p(d_t)$	$p(\underline{A}_t)$
		$p(B_t)$	$p(\underline{B}_t)$	+1

Remark 2.2. Pfizer Inc. and BioNTech SE announced on Monday, November 09, 2020 - 06:45am results from a Phase 3 COVID-19 vaccine trial with 43,538 participants which provides evidence that their vaccine (BNT162b2) is preventing COVID-19 in participants without evidence of prior SARS-CoV-2 infection. In toto, 170 confirmed cases of COVID-19 were evaluated, with 8 in the vaccine group versus 162 in the placebo group. The exclusion relationship can be calculated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(\text{Vaccine : BNT162b2} | \text{COVID - 19(infection)}) &\equiv p(b_t) + p(c_t) + p(d_t) \\
 &\equiv 1 - p(a_t) \\
 &\equiv 1 - \left(\frac{8}{43538} \right) \\
 &\equiv +0,99981625
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.34}$$

with a P Value = 0,000184.

2.2.8. The goodness of fit test of an exclusion relationship

Definition 2.8 (The χ^2 goodness of fit test of an exclusion relationship).

Under some well known circumstances, testing hypothesis about an exclusion relationship $p(A_t | B_t)$ is possible by the chi-square distribution (also chi-squared or $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution) too. The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of an exclusion relationship with degree of freedom (d. f.) of d. f. = 1 is calculated as

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}((A_t | B_t) | A) &\equiv \frac{(b - (a + b))^2}{A} + \frac{((c + d) - \underline{A})^2}{\underline{A}} \\ &\equiv \frac{a^2}{A} + 0 \\ &\equiv \frac{a^2}{A}\end{aligned}\tag{2.35}$$

or equally as

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}((A_t | B_t) | B) &\equiv \frac{(c - (a + c))^2}{B} + \frac{((b + d) - \underline{B})^2}{\underline{B}} \\ &\equiv \frac{a^2}{B} + 0 \\ &\equiv \frac{a^2}{B}\end{aligned}\tag{2.36}$$

and can be compared with a theoretical chi-square value at a certain level of significance α . The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution equals zero when the observed values are equal to the expected/theoretical values of an exclusion relationship/distribution $p(A_t | B_t)$, in which case the null hypothesis has to be accepted. Yate's (Yates, 1934) continuity correction was not used under these circumstances.

2.2.9. The left-tailed p Value of an exclusion relationship

Definition 2.9 (The left-tailed p Value of an exclusion relationship).

It is known that as a sample size, N , increases, a sampling distribution of a special test statistic approaches the normal distribution (central limit theorem). Under these circumstances, the left-tailed (lt) p Value (Barukčić, 2019c) of an exclusion relationship can be calculated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}p\text{Value}_{\text{lt}}(A_t | B_t) &\equiv 1 - e^{-(1-p(A_t|B_t))} \\ &\equiv 1 - e^{-(a/N)}\end{aligned}\tag{2.37}$$

A low p-value may provide some evidence of statistical significance.

2.2.10. Neither nor conditions

Definition 2.10 (Neither A_t nor B_t conditions [NOR]).

Mathematically, a neither A_t nor B_t condition (or rejection according to the French philosopher and logician Jean George Pierre Nicod (1893-1924), i.e. Jean Nicod's statement (Nicod, 1924)) relationship (NOR), denoted by $p(A_t \downarrow B_t)$ in terms of statistics and probability theory, is defined (Barukčić, 1989, p. 68-70) as

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(A_t \downarrow B_t) &\equiv p(d_t) \\
 &\equiv \frac{N - \sum_{t=1}^N (A_t \vee B_t)}{N} \equiv \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N (\underline{A}_t \wedge \underline{B}_t)}{N} \equiv \frac{N \times (p(d_t))}{N} \\
 &\equiv \frac{d}{N} \\
 &\equiv +1
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.38}$$

2.2.11. The Chi square goodness of fit test of a neither nor condition relationship

Definition 2.11 (The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a neither A_t nor B_t condition relationship).

A neither A_t nor B_t condition relationship $p(A_t \downarrow B_t)$ can be tested by the chi-square distribution (also chi-squared or $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution). The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a neither A_t nor B_t condition relationship with degree of freedom (d. f.) of d. f. = 1 may be calculated as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}((A_t \downarrow B_t) | A) &\equiv \frac{(d - (c + d))^2}{\underline{A}} + \\
 &\quad \frac{((a + b) - A)^2}{A} \\
 &\equiv \frac{c^2}{\underline{A}} + 0
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.39}$$

or equally as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}((A_t \downarrow B_t) | B) &\equiv \frac{(d - (b + d))^2}{\underline{B}} + \\
 &\quad \frac{((a + c) - B)^2}{B} \\
 &\equiv \frac{b^2}{\underline{B}} + 0
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.40}$$

Yate's (Yates, 1934) continuity correction has not been used in this context.

2.2.12. The left-tailed p Value of a neither nor B condition relationship

Definition 2.12 (The left-tailed p Value of a neither A_t nor B_t condition relationship).

The left-tailed (lt) p Value (Barukčić, 2019c) of a neither A_t nor B_t condition relationship can be

calculated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
 pValue_{1t}(A_t \downarrow B_t) &\equiv 1 - e^{-(1-p(A_t \downarrow B_t))} \\
 &\equiv 1 - e^{-p(A_t \vee B_t)} \\
 &\equiv 1 - e^{-((a+b+c)/N)}
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.41}$$

where \vee may denote disjunction or logical inclusive or. In this context, a low p-value indicates again a statistical significance. In general, it is $p(A_t \vee B_t) \equiv 1 - p(A_t \downarrow B_t)$ (see table 5).

Table 5. Neither A_t nor B_t relationship.

		Conditioned B_t		
		YES	NO	
Condition A_t	YES	0	0	0
	NO	0	1	1
		0	1	1

2.2.13. Necessary condition

Definition 2.13 (Necessary condition [*Conditio sine qua non*]).

Mathematically, the necessary condition (SINE) relationship, denoted by $p(A_t \leftarrow B_t)$ in terms of statistics and probability theory, is defined (Barukčić, 1989, p. 15-28) as

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(A_t \leftarrow B_t) &\equiv p(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t) \equiv \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N (A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)}{N} \equiv \frac{(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t) \times p(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)}{(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)} \\
 &\equiv p(a_t) + p(b_t) + p(d_t) \\
 &\equiv \frac{N \times (p(a_t) + p(b_t) + p(d_t))}{N} \equiv \frac{E(A_t \leftarrow B_t)}{N} \\
 &\equiv \frac{a + b + d}{N} \equiv \frac{E(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)}{N} \\
 &\equiv \frac{A + d}{N} \equiv \frac{E(A_t \leftarrow B_t)}{N} \\
 &\equiv \frac{a + B}{N} \equiv \frac{E(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)}{N} \\
 &\equiv +1
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.42}$$

where $E(A_t \leftarrow B_t) \equiv E(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)$ indicates the expectation value of the necessary condition. In general, it is $p(A_t \leftarrow B_t) \equiv 1 - p(A_t \downarrow B_t)$ (see Table 6).

Remark 2.3. A necessary condition A_t is characterized itself by the property that another event B_t will not occur if A_t is not given, if A_t did not occur (Barukčić, 1989, 1997, 2005, 2016, 2017a,b, 2020a; Barukčić and Ufuoma, 2020a; Barukčić, 2020b,c,d). **Example.** A human being cannot live

Table 6. Necessary condition.

		Conditioned B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition	TRUE	$p(a_t)$	$p(b_t)$	$p(A_t)$
A_t	FALSE	+0	$p(d_t)$	$p(\underline{A}_t)$
		$p(B_t)$	$p(\underline{B}_t)$	+1

without water. A human being cannot live without gaseous oxygen et cetera. Water itself is a necessary condition of human life. However, gaseous oxygen is a necessary condition of human life too. Thus far, even if water is given and even if water is a necessary condition of human life, without gaseous oxygen there will be no human life. In general, if a conditioned or an outcome B_t depends on the necessary condition A_t and equally on numerous other necessary conditions, an event B_t will not occur if A_t itself is not given independently of the occurrence of other necessary conditions.

2.2.14. The Chi-square goodness of fit test of a necessary condition relationship

Definition 2.14 (The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a necessary condition relationship).

Under some well known circumstances, hypothesis about the conditio sine qua non relationship $p(A_t \leftarrow B_t)$ can be tested by the chi-square distribution (also chi-squared or χ^2 -distribution), first described by the German statistician Friedrich Robert Helmert (Helmert, 1876) and later rediscovered by Karl Pearson (Pearson, 1900) in the context of a goodness of fit test. The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a conditio sine qua non relationship with degree of freedom (d. f.) of d. f. = 1 is calculated as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \leftarrow B_t | B) &\equiv \frac{(a - (a + c))^2}{B} + \frac{((b + d) - \underline{B})^2}{\underline{B}} \\
 &\equiv \frac{c^2}{B} + 0 \\
 &\equiv \frac{c^2}{B}
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.43}$$

or equally as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \leftarrow B_t | \underline{A}) &\equiv \frac{(d - (c + d))^2}{\underline{A}} + \frac{((a + b) - A)^2}{A} \\
 &\equiv \frac{c^2}{\underline{A}} + 0 \\
 &\equiv \frac{c^2}{\underline{A}}
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.44}$$

and can be compared with a theoretical chi-square value at a certain level of significance α . It has not yet been finally clarified whether the use of Yate's (Yates, 1934) continuity correction is necessary at all.

2.2.15. The left-tailed p Value of the conditio sine qua non relationship

Definition 2.15 (The left-tailed p Value of the conditio sine qua non relationship).

The left-tailed (lt) p Value (Barukčić, 2019c) of the conditio sine qua non relationship can be calculated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} pValue_{lt}(A_t \leftarrow B_t) &\equiv 1 - e^{-(1-p(A_t \leftarrow B_t))} \\ &\equiv 1 - e^{-(c/N)} \end{aligned} \quad (2.45)$$

2.2.16. Sufficient condition

Definition 2.16 (Sufficient condition [*Conditio per quam*]).

Mathematically, the sufficient condition (IMP) relationship, denoted by $p(A_t \rightarrow B_t)$ in terms of statistics and probability theory, is defined (Barukčić, 1989, p. 68-70) as

$$\begin{aligned} p(A_t \rightarrow B_t) &\equiv p(\underline{A}_t \vee B_t) \equiv \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N (\underline{A}_t \vee B_t)}{N} \equiv \frac{(\underline{A}_t \vee B_t) \times p(\underline{A}_t \vee B_t)}{(\underline{A}_t \vee B_t)} \\ &\equiv p(a_t) + p(c_t) + p(d_t) \\ &\equiv \frac{N \times (p(a_t) + p(c_t) + p(d_t))}{N} \\ &\equiv \frac{a + c + d}{N} \equiv \frac{E(\underline{A}_t \vee B_t)}{N} \\ &\equiv \frac{B + d}{N} \equiv \frac{E(A_t \rightarrow B_t)}{N} \\ &\equiv \frac{a + \underline{A}}{N} \\ &\equiv +1 \end{aligned} \quad (2.46)$$

It is $p(A_t \succ B_t) \equiv 1 - p(A_t \rightarrow B_t)$ (see Table 7).

Table 7. Sufficient condition.

		Conditioned B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition	TRUE	$p(a_t)$	+0	$p(A_t)$
	FALSE	$p(c_t)$	$p(d_t)$	$p(\underline{A}_t)$
		$p(B_t)$	$p(\underline{B}_t)$	+1

Remark 2.4. A sufficient condition A_t is characterized by the property that another event B_t will occur if A_t is given, if A_t itself occurred (Barukčić, 1989, 1997, 2005, 2016, 2017a,b, 2020a; Barukčić and Ufuoma, 2020a; Barukčić, 2020b,c,d). **Example.** The ground, the streets, the trees, human beings and many other objects too will become wet during heavy rain. Especially, **if** it is raining (event A_t), **then** human beings will become wet (event B_t). However, even if this is a common human wisdom, a human being equipped with an appropriate umbrella (denoted by R_t) need not become wet even during heavy rain. An appropriate umbrella (R_t) is similar to an event with the potential to counteract the occurrence of another event (B_t) and can be understood something as an **anti-dot** of another event. In other words, an appropriate umbrella is an antidote of the effect of rain on human body, an appropriate umbrella has the potential to protect humans from the effect of rain on their body. It is a good rule of thumb that the following relationship

$$p(A_t \rightarrow B_t) + p(R_t \wedge B_t) \equiv +1 \quad (2.47)$$

indicates that R_t is an antidote of A_t . However, taking a shower, swimming in a lake et cetera may make human hair wet too. More than anything else, however, these events does not affect the final outcome, the effect of raining on human body.

2.2.17. The Chi square goodness of fit test of a sufficient condition relationship

Definition 2.17 (The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a sufficient condition relationship).

Under some well known circumstances, testing hypothesis about the conditio per quam relationship $p(A_t \rightarrow B_t)$ is possible by the chi-square distribution (also chi-squared or $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution) too. The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a conditio per quam relationship with degree of freedom (d. f.) of d. f. = 1 is calculated as

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \rightarrow B_t | A) &\equiv \frac{(a - (a+b))^2}{A} + \frac{((c+d) - \underline{A})^2}{\underline{A}} \\ &\equiv \frac{b^2}{A} + 0 \\ &\equiv \frac{b^2}{A} \end{aligned} \quad (2.48)$$

or equally as

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \rightarrow B_t | B) &\equiv \frac{(d - (b+d))^2}{B} + \frac{((a+c) - B)^2}{B} \\ &\equiv \frac{b^2}{B} + 0 \\ &\equiv \frac{b^2}{B} \end{aligned} \quad (2.49)$$

and can be compared with a theoretical chi-square value at a certain level of significance α . The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution equals zero when the observed values are equal to the expected/theoretical values of the conditio per quam relationship/distribution $p(A_t \rightarrow B_t)$, in which case the null hypothesis is accepted. Yate's (Yates, 1934) continuity correction has not been used in this context.

2.2.18. The left-tailed p Value of the conditio per quam relationship

Definition 2.18 (The left-tailed p Value of the conditio per quam relationship).

The left-tailed (lt) p Value (Barukčić, 2019c) of the conditio per quam relationship can be calculated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} pValue_{lt}(A_t \rightarrow B_t) &\equiv 1 - e^{-(1-p(A_t \rightarrow B_t))} \\ &\equiv 1 - e^{-(b/N)} \end{aligned} \quad (2.50)$$

Again, a low p-value indicates a statistical significance.

2.2.19. Necessary and sufficient conditions

Definition 2.19 (Necessary and sufficient conditions [EQV]).

The necessary and sufficient condition (EQV) relationship, denoted by $p(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t)$ in terms of statistics and probability theory, is defined (Barukčić, 1989, p. 68-70) as

$$\begin{aligned} p(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t) &\equiv \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N ((A_t \vee \underline{B}_t) \wedge (\underline{A}_t \vee B_t))}{N} \\ &\equiv p(a_t) + p(d_t) \\ &\equiv \frac{N \times (p(a_t) + p(d_t))}{N} \\ &\equiv \frac{a + d}{N} \\ &\equiv +1 \end{aligned} \quad (2.51)$$

2.2.20. The Chi square goodness of fit test of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship

Definition 2.20 (The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship).

Even the necessary and sufficient condition relationship $p(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t)$ can be tested by the chi-square distribution (also chi-squared or $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution) too. The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship with degree of freedom (d. f.) of d. f. = 1 is calculated as

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t | A) &\equiv \frac{(a - (a+b))^2}{A} + \\ &\quad \frac{d - ((c+d))^2}{\frac{A}{d}} \\ &\equiv \frac{b^2}{A} + \frac{c^2}{\frac{A}{d}} \end{aligned} \quad (2.52)$$

or equally as

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t | B) &\equiv \frac{(a - (a + c))^2}{B} + \frac{d - ((b + d))^2}{B} \\ &\equiv \frac{c^2}{B} + \frac{b^2}{B}\end{aligned}\quad (2.53)$$

The calculated $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship can be compared with a theoretical chi-square value at a certain level of significance α . Under conditions where the observed values are equal to the expected/theoretical values of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship/distribution $p(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t)$, the $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution equals zero. It is to be cleared whether Yate's (Yates, 1934) continuity correction should be used at all.

2.2.21. The left-tailed p Value of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship

Definition 2.21 (The left-tailed p Value of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship).

The left-tailed (lt) p Value (Barukčić, 2019c) of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship can be calculated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}pValue_{lt}(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t) &\equiv 1 - e^{-(1-p(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t))} \\ &\equiv 1 - e^{-((b+c)/N)}\end{aligned}\quad (2.54)$$

In this context, a low p-value indicates again a statistical significance. Table 8 may provide an overview of the theoretical distribution of a necessary and sufficient condition.

Table 8. Necessary and sufficient condition.

		Conditioned B_t		
		YES	NO	
Condition A_t	YES	1	0	1
	NO	0	1	1
		1	1	2

2.2.22. Either or conditions

Definition 2.22 (Either A_t or B_t conditions [NEQV]).

Mathematically, an either A_t or B_t condition relationship (NEQV), denoted by $p(A_t \succcurlyeq B_t)$ in terms

of statistics and probability theory, is defined (Barukčić, 1989, p. 68-70) as

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(A_t \succ B_t) &\equiv \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N ((A_t \wedge \underline{B}_t) \vee (\underline{A}_t \wedge B_t))}{N} \\
 &\equiv p(b_t) + p(c_t) \\
 &\equiv \frac{N \times (p(b_t) + p(c_t))}{N} \\
 &\equiv \frac{b + c}{N} \\
 &\equiv +1
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.55}$$

It is $p(A_t \succ B_t) \equiv 1 - p(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t)$ (see Table 9).

Table 9. Either A_t or B_t relationship.

		Conditioned B_t		
		YES	NO	
Condition A_t	YES	0	1	1
	NO	1	0	1
		1	1	2

2.2.23. The Chi-square goodness of fit test of an either or condition relationship

Definition 2.23 (The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of an either or condition relationship).

An either or condition relationship $p(A_t \succ B_t)$ can be tested by the chi-square distribution (also chi-squared or $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution) too. The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of an either or condition relationship with degree of freedom (d. f.) of d. f. = 1 is calculated as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}((A_t \succ B_t) | A) &\equiv \frac{(b - (a + b))^2}{A} + \\
 &\quad \frac{c - ((c + d))^2}{\underline{A}} \\
 &\equiv \frac{a^2}{A} + \frac{d^2}{\underline{A}}
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.56}$$

or equally as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}((A_t \succ B_t) | B) &\equiv \frac{(c - (a + c))^2}{B} + \\
 &\quad \frac{b - ((b + d))^2}{\underline{B}} \\
 &\equiv \frac{a^2}{B} + \frac{d^2}{\underline{B}}
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.57}$$

Yate's (Yates, 1934) continuity correction has not been used in this context.

2.2.24. The left-tailed p Value of an either or condition relationship

Definition 2.24 (The left-tailed p Value of an either or condition relationship).

The left-tailed (lt) p Value (Barukčić, 2019c) of an either or condition relationship can be calculated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} pValue_{lt}(A_t \succ B_t) &\equiv 1 - e^{-(1-p(A_t > B_t))} \\ &\equiv 1 - e^{-((a+d)/N)} \end{aligned} \quad (2.58)$$

In this context, a low p-value indicates again a statistical significance.

2.2.25. Causal relationship k

Definition 2.25 (Causal relationship k).

Nonetheless, mathematically, the causal (Barukčić, 2011a,b, 2012) relationship (Barukčić, 1989, 1997, 2005, 2016, 2017a) between a cause U_t (German: Ursache) and an effect W_t (German: Wirkung), denoted by $k(U_t, W_t)$, is defined at each single Bernoulli trial t in terms of statistics and probability theory as

$$\begin{aligned} k(U_t, W_t) &\equiv \frac{\sigma(U_t, W_t)}{\sigma(U_t) \times \sigma(W_t)} \\ &\equiv \frac{p(U_t \wedge W_t) - p(U_t) \times p(W_t)}{\sqrt{(p(U_t) \times (1 - p(U_t))) \times (p(W_t) \times (1 - p(W_t)))}} \end{aligned} \quad (2.59)$$

where $\sigma(U_t, W_t)$ denotes the co-variance between a cause U_t and an effect W_t at every single Bernoulli trial t , $\sigma(U_t)$ denotes the standard deviation of a cause U_t at the same single Bernoulli trial t , $\sigma(W_t)$ denotes the standard deviation of an effect W_t at same single Bernoulli trial t . Table 10 illustrates the theoretically possible relationships between a cause and an effect.

Table 10. Sample space and the causal relationship k

		Effect B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Cause A_t	TRUE	$p(a_t)$	$p(b_t)$	$p(U_t)$
	FALSE	$p(c_t)$	$p(d_t)$	$p(\underline{U}_t)$
		$p(W_t)$	$p(\underline{W}_t)$	+1

2.2.26. Cause and effect

Definition 2.26 (Cause and effect).

Table 11. What is the cause, what is the effect?

		Effect W_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Cause	TRUE	+1	+0	$p(U_t)$
U_t	FALSE	+0	+1	$p(\underline{U}_t)$
		$p(W_t)$	$p(\underline{W}_t)$	+1

What is the cause, what is the effect? Under conditions of a **positive** causal relationship k , an event U_t which is for sure a cause of another event W_t is at the same time t a necessary and sufficient condition of an event W_t . Table 11 may illustrate this relationship.

The collapse and the logical inconsistency of the relative risk under these circumstances is obvious.

As can be seen, there is a kind of strange mirroring between U_t and W_t . Lastly, both are converses of each other too. In other words, U_t 's being a necessary condition of W_t 's is equivalent to W_t 's being a sufficient condition of U_t 's (and vice versa). In general, it is

$$(U_t \vee \underline{W}_t) \equiv (\underline{W}_t \vee U_t) \equiv ((U_t \vee \underline{W}_t) \wedge (\underline{W}_t \vee U_t)) \equiv +1 \quad (2.60)$$

In our everyday words,

without

U_t

no

W_t

is equivalent with

if

W_t

then

U_t

and vice versa.

Necessary and sufficient conditions are relationships used to describe the relationship between two events at the same Bernoulli trial t . In more detail, if U_t then W_t is equivalent with W_t is necessary for U_t , because the truth of U_t guarantees the truth of W_t . In general, it is

$$(\underline{U}_t \vee W_t) \equiv (W_t \vee \underline{U}_t) \equiv ((\underline{U}_t \vee W_t) \wedge (W_t \vee \underline{U}_t)) \equiv +1 \quad (2.61)$$

In other words, it is impossible to have U_t without W_t (Bloch, 2011). Similarly, U_t is sufficient for W_t , because U_t being true always implies that W_t is true, but U_t not being true does not always imply that W_t is not true.

For instance, **without** gaseous oxygen (U_t), there would be **no** burning wax candle (W_t); hence the relationship **if** burning wax candle (W_t) **then** gaseous oxygen (U_t) is equally true and given.

This simple example may illustrate the reason why a sufficient condition alone is not enough to describe a cause completely. The relationship **if** burning wax candle (W_t) **then** gaseous oxygen (U_t) is given. Independently of this fact, a burning wax candle is not the cause of gaseous oxygen. Therefore,

in order to be a cause of oxygen, additional evidence is necessary that a burning wax candle is a necessary condition of gaseous oxygen too. However, even if the relationship **without** gaseous oxygen **no** burning wax candle is given, this relationship is not given vice versa. The relationship **without** burning wax candle **no** gaseous oxygen is not given. Like other fundamental concepts, the concepts of cause and effect can be associated with difficulties too. In order to recognise a causal relationship between U_t and W_t , it is necessary that the same study or that at least different studies provide evidence of a necessary condition between U_t and W_t and of a sufficient condition between U_t and W_t and if possible of a **necessary and sufficient condition** between U_t and W_t too.

Mathematically, a necessary and sufficient condition between U_t and W_t is defined as

$$(U_t \vee \underline{W}_t) \wedge (\underline{U}_t \vee W_t) \equiv +1 \quad (2.62)$$

However, I think it necessary to make a clear distinction between a necessary and sufficient condition and the converse relationship (Eq. 2.60) above.

$$((U_t \vee \underline{W}_t) \wedge (\underline{W}_t \vee U_t)) \neq (U_t \vee \underline{W}_t) \wedge (\underline{U}_t \vee W_t) \quad (2.63)$$

2.2.27. Study design and bias

Systematic observation and experimentation, inductive and deductive reasoning are essential for any formation and testing of hypotheses and theories about the natural world. In one way or another, logically and mathematically sound scientific methods and concepts are crucial constituents of any scientific progress. When all goes well, different scientists at different times and places using the same scientific methodology should be able to generate the same scientific knowledge. However, more than half (52%) of scientists surveyed believe that studies do not successfully reproduce sufficiently similar or the same results as the original studies (Baker, 2016). In a very large study on publication bias in meta-analyses, Kicinski et al. (Kicinski et al., 2015) found evidence of publication bias even in systematic reviews. Therefore, a careful re-evaluation of the study/experimental design, the statistical methods and other scientific means which underpin scientific inquiry and research goals appears to be necessary once and again. While it is important to recognise the shortcoming of today's science, one issue which has shaped debates over studies published is the question: **has a study really measured what it set out to?** Even if studies carried out can vary greatly in detail, the data from the studies itself provide information about the credibility of the data.

Index of unfairness (IOU)

Definition 2.27 (Index of unfairness).

The index of unfairness (Barukčić, 2019a) (IOU) is defined as

$$p(\text{IOU}(A, B)) \equiv \text{Absolute} \left(\left(\frac{A+B}{N} \right) - 1 \right) \quad (2.64)$$

A very good study design should assure as much as possible a $p(\text{IOU}) = 0$. In point of fact, against the background of lacking enough experience with the use of $p(\text{IOU})$, a $p(\text{IOU})$ up to 0.25 could be of use too. An index of unfairness is of use to prove whether sample data are biased and whether sample data can be used for Chi-square based analysis of necessary conditions, of sufficient conditions and of causal relationships.

Index of independence (IOI)

Definition 2.28 (Index of independence).

The index of independence (Barukčić, 2019b) (IOI) is defined as

$$p(\text{IOI}(A, \underline{B})) \equiv \text{Absolute} \left(\left(\frac{A + B}{N} \right) - 1 \right) \quad (2.65)$$

A very good study design which aims to prove **an exclusion relationship or a causal relationship** should assure as much as possible a $p(\text{IOI}) = 0$. However, once again, against the background of lacking enough experience with the use of $p(\text{IOI})$, sample data with a $p(\text{IOI})$ up to 0.25 are of use too. Today, most double-blind placebo-controlled studies are based on the demand that **$p(\text{IOU}) = p(\text{IOI})$** while the value of $p(\text{IOU})$ of has been widely neglected. Such an approach leads to unnecessary big sample sizes, the increase of cost, the waste of time and, most importantly of all, to epistemological systematically biased sample data and conclusions drawn. A change is necessary.

Index of relationship (IOR)

Definition 2.29 (Index of relationship (IOR)).

Due to several reasons, it is not always easy to identify the unique characteristics between two events like A_t and B_t . And more than that, it is difficult to decide what to do, and much more difficult to know in which direction one should think and which decision is right. Sometimes it is helpful to know at least something about the direction of the relationship between two events like A_t and B_t . Under conditions where $p(a_t) = p(A_t \wedge B_t)$, the index of relationship (Barukčić, 2021a), abbreviated as IOR, is defined as

$$\begin{aligned} \text{IOR}(A_t, B_t) &\equiv \left(\frac{p(A_t \wedge B_t)}{p(B_t) \times p(A_t)} \right) - 1 \\ &\equiv \left(\frac{p(a_t)}{p(B_t) \times p(A_t)} \right) - 1 \\ &\equiv \left(\left(\frac{N \times N \times p(a_t)}{N \times p(B_t) \times N \times p(A_t)} \right) - 1 \right) \\ &\equiv \left(\left(\frac{N \times a}{A \times B} \right) - 1 \right) \end{aligned} \quad (2.66)$$

where $p(A_t)$ denotes the probability of an event A_t at the Bernoulli trial t and $p(B_t)$ denotes the probability of another event B_t at the same Bernoulli trial t while $p(a_t)$ denotes the joint probability of $p(A_t \text{ AND } B_t)$ at the same Bernoulli trial t and a , A and B may denote the expectation values.

2.2.28. relative risk (RR)

Relative risk (RR_{nc})

Definition 2.30 (Relative risk (RR_{nc})).

The degree of association between the two binomial variables can be assessed by a number of very different coefficients, the relative (Cornfield, 1951; Sadowsky et al., 1953) risk is one (Barukčić, 2021b) of them. In general, relative risk RR_{nc} , which provides some evidence of a necessary condition, is defined as

$$RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc} = \frac{\frac{p(a_t)}{p(A_t)}}{\frac{p(c_t)}{p(NotA_t)}} = \frac{p(a_t) \times p(NotA_t)}{p(c_t) \times p(A_t)} = \frac{N \times p(a_t) \times N \times p(NotA_t)}{N \times p(c_t) \times N \times p(A_t)} = \frac{a_t \times (NotA_t)}{c_t \times A_t} = \frac{EER(A_t, B_t)}{CER(A_t, B_t)} \quad (2.67)$$

That what scientist generally understand by relative risk is the ratio of a probability of an event occurring with an exposure versus the probability of an event occurring without an exposure. In other words,

relative risk = (probability(event in exposed group)) / (probability(the same event in not exposed group)).

A $RR(A_t, B_t) = +1$ means that exposure does not affect the outcome or both are independent of each other while $RR(A_t, B_t)$ less than +1 means that the risk of the outcome is decreased by the exposure. In this context, an $RR(A_t, B_t)$ greater than +1 denotes that the risk of the outcome is increased by the exposure. Widely known problems with odds ratio and relative risk are already documented in literature.

Relative risk (RR (sc))

Definition 2.31 (Relative risk (RR (sc))).

The relative risk (sc), which provides some evidence of a sufficient condition, is calculated from the point of view of an outcome and is defined as

$$RR(A_t, B_t)_{sc} = \frac{\frac{p(a_t)}{p(B_t)}}{\frac{p(b_t)}{p(NotB_t)}} = \frac{p(a_t) \times p(NotB_t)}{p(b_t) \times p(B_t)} = \frac{N \times p(a_t) \times N \times p(NotB_t)}{N \times p(b_t) \times N \times p(B_t)} = \frac{a_t \times (NotB_t)}{b_t \times B_t} = \frac{OPR(A_t, B_t)}{CPR(A_t, B_t)} \quad (2.68)$$

Example.

Tugwell et al. (Tugwell et al., 2004) investigated a chickenpox outbreak in an Oregon elementary school in October 2001. "Twenty-one cases occurred in 9 of 16 classrooms. In these 9 classrooms, 18 of 152 (12%) vaccinated students developed chickenpox, compared with 3 of 7 (43%) unvaccinated students." These data are illustrated by the following two by two table.

Table 12. Outbreak of varicella (chickenpox) in Oregon in 2001

		Varicella B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Vaccinated A_t	TRUE	$a_t = 18$	$b_t = 134$	$A_t = 152$
	FALSE	$c_t = 3$	$d_t = 4$	$\underline{A}_t = 7$
		$B_t = 21$	$\underline{B}_t = 138$	$N_t = 159$

The relative risk RR_{nc} is calculated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
 RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc} &\equiv \frac{\frac{p(a_t)}{p(A_t)}}{\frac{p(c_t)}{p(NotA_t)}} = \frac{p(a_t) \times p(NotA_t)}{p(A_t) \times p(c_t)} \\
 &\equiv \left(\frac{a_t \times \underline{A}_t}{c_t \times A_t} \right) \\
 &\equiv \left(\frac{18 \times 7}{3 \times 152} \right) \\
 &\equiv \frac{0.118}{0.42} \\
 &\equiv 0.28
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.69}$$

The relative risk is $RR_{nc} = +0.28$ and less than 1.0 which indicates that a vaccination has not been a necessary condition for the outbreak observed. Quite the opposite, a decreased risk or a protective effect for the children which were vaccinated (exposed to vaccine) is documented. However, the relative risk of $RR_{nc} = +0.28$ is completely misleading in this context, as can be seen by table 13.

Table 13. Vaccinated and Chickenpox outbreak (Study of Tugwell et al., 2004).

		Chickenpox		
		YES	NO	
Vaccinated	YES	18	134	152
	NO	3	4	7
		21	138	159
Causal relationship k =		-0,1879290573		
p Value left tailed (HGD) =		0,0493451		
p (SINE) =		0,9811320755		
$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE — B _t) =		0,4286		
$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE — A _t) =		1,2857		
p Value (SINE) =		0,0186910395		
p (EXCL) =		0,8867924528		
$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL— A _t) =		2,1316		
$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL— B _t) =		15,4286		
p Value (EXCL) =		0,1070346915		
OR =		0,1384		
RR (nc) =		0,2763		
RR (sc) =		0,8827		
IOR =		-0,1034		
p(IOI)=		0,823899371		
p(IOU)=		0,088050314		
Vaccine efficacy (%) =		72,3684		

The data as published by Tugwell et al. (Tugwell et al., 2004) are self-contradictory. There is some evidence that the vaccination itself has not been responsible for the outbreak of varicella (chickenpox) in Oregon (USA) in 2001 ($k < +0$; p Value left tailed (HGD)=0,0493451). However, the exclusion relationship is p (EXCL)=0,8867924528 and not significant. Nonetheless, the data presented does not support the conclusion that the vaccination prevents from the outbreak of varicella (chickenpox). The index of independence (p(IOI)) is p(IOI) = 0,823899371. In other words, the study design of the study of Tugwell et al. (Tugwell et al., 2004) has been extremely unfair in this respect. Altogether, it cannot be excluded that the data are potentially biased.

The question is justified, has the vaccination against varicella (chickenpox) been responsible for the outbreak of varicella (chickenpox) in Oregon (USA) in 2001? Taking the data as published by Tugwell et al. (Tugwell et al., 2004) for granted, we need to conclude the following: yes!

Without vaccination against varicella (chickenpox) in an Oregon elementary school in 2001 **no** outbreak of varicella (chickenpox) (p(SINE) = 0,9811; p Value (SINE) = 0,0187; p(IOU)= 0,0881 et cetera).

However, is such a conclusion (Barukčić, 2021c) really inevitable, completely justified and free of any errors?

The study design is acceptable (p(IOU)= 0,0881) and indicates that the data presented are of use

for the analysis of a *conditio sine qua non* relationship. However, a negative causal relationship k ($k = -0,1879$), even if $p(\text{IOU}) = 0,0881$ is very impressive, does not support the hypothesis of necessary condition at all. In other words, the data as presented by Tugwell et al. (Tugwell et al., 2004) are self-contradictory and we cannot draw any valuable conclusion out of the same. Unfortunately, the close connection between vaccination and outbreak of varicella (chickenpox) in Oregon in 2001 is rather masked than discovered by the relative risk. Even though it is considered highly desirable, the conclusion that the vaccination protected against an outbreak of varicella (chickenpox) in Oregon (USA) in 2001 is not justified for sure due to the data published.

Relative risk reduction (RRR)

Definition 2.32 (Relative risk reduction (RRR)).

$$\begin{aligned} RRR(A_t, B_t) &\equiv \frac{CER(A_t, B_t) - EER(A_t, B_t)}{CER(A_t, B_t)} \\ &= 1 - RR(A_t, B_t) \end{aligned} \quad (2.70)$$

Vaccine efficacy (VE)

Definition 2.33 (Vaccine efficacy (VE)).

Vaccine efficacy is defined as the percentage reduction of a disease in a vaccinated group of people as compared to an unvaccinated group of people.

$$\begin{aligned} VE(A_t, B_t) &\equiv 100 \times (1 - RR(A_t, B_t)) \\ &\equiv 100 \times \left(\frac{CER(A_t, B_t) - EER(A_t, B_t)}{CER(A_t, B_t)} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (2.71)$$

Historically, vaccine efficacy has been designed to evaluate the efficacy of a certain vaccine by Greenwood and Yule in 1915 for the cholera and typhoid vaccines (Greenwood and Yule, 1915) and best measured using double-blind, randomized, clinical controlled trials. However, the calculated vaccine efficacy is depending too much on the study design, can lead to erroneous conclusions and is only of very limited value.

Experimental event rate (EER)

Definition 2.34 (Experimental event rate (EER)).

$$EER(A_t, B_t) \equiv \frac{p(a_t)}{p(A_t)} = \frac{a_t}{a_t + b_t} \quad (2.72)$$

Definition 2.35 (Control event rate (CER)).

$$CER(A_t, B_t) \equiv \frac{p(c_t)}{p(\underline{A}_t)} = \frac{c_t}{c_t + d_t} \quad (2.73)$$

Absolute risk reduction (ARR)

Definition 2.36 (Absolute risk reduction (ARR)).

$$\begin{aligned} ARR(A_t, B_t) &\equiv \frac{p(c_t)}{p(\underline{A}_t)} - \frac{p(a_t)}{p(A_t)} \\ &= \frac{c_t}{c_t + d_t} - \frac{a_t}{a_t + b_t} \\ &= CER(A_t, B_t) - EER(A_t, B_t) \end{aligned} \quad (2.74)$$

Absolute risk increase (ARI)

Definition 2.37 (Absolute risk increase (ARI)).

$$\begin{aligned} ARI(A_t, B_t) &\equiv \frac{p(a_t)}{p(A_t)} - \frac{p(c_t)}{p(\underline{A}_t)} \\ &= EER(A_t, B_t) - CER(A_t, B_t) \end{aligned} \quad (2.75)$$

Number needed to treat (NNT)

Definition 2.38 (Number needed to treat (NNT)).

$$NNT(A_t, B_t) \equiv \frac{1}{CER(A_t, B_t) - EER(A_t, B_t)} \quad (2.76)$$

An ideal number needed to treat (Laupacis et al., 1988; Cook and Sackett, 1995), mathematically the reciprocal of the absolute risk reduction, is $NNT = 1$. Under these circumstances, everyone improves with a treatment, while no one improves with control. A higher number needed to treat indicates more or less a treatment which is less effective.

Number needed to harm (NNH)

Definition 2.39 (Number needed to harm (NNH)).

$$NNH(A_t, B_t) \equiv \frac{1}{EER(A_t, B_t) - CER(A_t, B_t)} \quad (2.77)$$

The number needed to harm (Massel and Cruickshank, 2002), mathematically the inverse of the absolute risk increase, indicates at the end how many patients need to be exposed to a certain factor, in order to observe a harm in one patient that would not otherwise have been harmed.

Outcome prevalence rate (OPR)

Definition 2.40 (Outcome prevalence rate (OPR)).

$$OPR(A_t, B_t) \equiv \frac{p(a_t)}{p(B_t)} = \frac{a_t}{a_t + c_t} \quad (2.78)$$

Control prevalence rate (CPR)

Definition 2.41 (Control prevalence rate (CPR)).

$$CPR(A_t, B_t) \equiv \frac{p(b_t)}{p(\underline{B}_t)} = \frac{b_t}{b_t + d_t} \quad (2.79)$$

Bias and confounding is present to some degree in all research. In order to assess the relationship of exposure with a disease or an outcome, a fictive control group (i.e. of newborn or of young children et cetera) can be of use too. Under certain circumstances, even a $CPR = 0$ is imaginable.

Absolute prevalence reduction (APR)

Definition 2.42 (Absolute prevalence reduction (APR)).

$$APR(A_t, B_t) \equiv CPR(A_t, B_t) - OPR(A_t, B_t) \quad (2.80)$$

Absolute prevalence increase (API)

Definition 2.43 (Absolute prevalence increase (API)).

$$API(A_t, B_t) \equiv OPR(A_t, B_t) - CPR(A_t, B_t) \quad (2.81)$$

Relative prevalence reduction (RPR)

Definition 2.44 (Relative prevalence reduction (RPR)).

$$\begin{aligned} RPR(A_t, B_t) &\equiv \frac{CPR(A_t, B_t) - OPR(A_t, B_t)}{CPR(A_t, B_t)} \\ &= 1 - RR(A_t, B_t)_{sc} \end{aligned} \quad (2.82)$$

The index NNS

Definition 2.45 (The index NNS).

$$NNS(A_t, B_t) \equiv \frac{1}{CPR(A_t, B_t) - OPR(A_t, B_t)} \quad (2.83)$$

Mathematically, the index NNS is the reciprocal of the absolute prevalence reduction.

The index NNI

Definition 2.46 (The index NNI).

$$NNI(A_t, B_t) \equiv \frac{1}{OPR(A_t, B_t) - CPR(A_t, B_t)} \quad (2.84)$$

Mathematically, the index NNI is the reciprocal of the absolute prevalence increase.

2.2.29. Odds ratio (OR)

Definition 2.47 (Odds ratio (OR)).

Odds ratios as an appropriate measure for estimating the relative risk have become widely used in medical reports of case-control studies. The odds ratio (Fisher, 1935, p. 50) is defined (Cox, 1958) as the ratio of the odds of an event occurring in one group with respect to the odds of its occurring in another group. Odds (Yule and Pearson, 1900, p. 273) ratio (OR) is a measure of association which quantifies the relationship between two binomial distributed random variables (exposure vs. outcome) and is related to Yule's (Yule and Pearson, 1900, p. 272) Q (Yule, 1912, p. 585/586). Two events A_t and B_t are regarded as independent if $(A_t, B_t) = 1$. Let

a_t = number of persons exposed to A_t and with disease B_t

b_t = number of persons exposed to A_t but without disease B_t

c_t = number of persons unexposed A_t but with disease B_t

d_t = number of persons unexposed A_t : and without disease B_t

$a_t + c_t$ = total number of persons with disease B_t (case-patients)

$b_t + d_t$ = total number of persons without disease B_t (controls).

Hereafter, consider the table 14. The odds' ratio (OR) is defined as

Table 14. The two by two table of random variables

		Conditioned/Outcome B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition/Exposure A_t	TRUE	a_t	b_t	A_t
	FALSE	c_t	d_t	\underline{A}_t
		B_t	\underline{B}_t	N_t

$$\begin{aligned}
 OR(A_t, B_t) &\equiv \left(\frac{a_t}{b_t}\right) / \left(\frac{c_t}{d_t}\right) \\
 &\equiv \left(\frac{a_t \times d_t}{b_t \times c_t}\right)
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{2.85}$$

Remark 2.5. Odds ratios can support logical fallacies and cause difficulties in drawing logically consistent conclusions. The chorus of voices is growing, which demand the immediate ending (Sackett et al., 1996; Knol, 2012) of any use of Odds ratio.

Under conditions where ($b = 0$), the measure of association odds ratio will collapse, because we need to divide by zero, as can be seen at eq. 2.85. However, according to today's rules of mathematics, a division by zero is neither allowed nor generally accepted as possible. It does no harm to remind ourselves that in the case $b = 0$ the event A_t is a sufficient condition of B_t . In other words, odds ratio is not able to recognize elementary relationships of objective reality. In fact, it would be a failure not to recognize how dangerous and less valuable odds ratio is.

Under conditions where ($c = 0$) odds ratio collapses too, because we need again to divide by zero, as can be seen at eq. 2.85. However, and again, today's rules of mathematics don't allow us a division by zero. In point of fact, in the case $c = 0$ it is more than necessary to point out that A_t is a necessary condition of B_t . In other words, odds ratio or the cross-product ratio is not able to recognize elementary relationships of nature like necessary conditions. We can and need to overcome all the epistemological obstacles as backed by odds ratio entirety. Sooner rather than later, we should give up this measure of relationship completely.

The probability of the necessary (Barukčić, 2021c) condition p(SINE) has been calculated and tested for statistical significance. The probability of the sufficient (Barukčić, 2021c) condition p(IMP) has been calculated, the statistical significance of this relationship has been proofed. The chi-square goodness of fit test with one degree of freedom has been used to test whether the sample data published fit a certain theoretical distribution in the population. The causal relationship k (Barukčić, 2021c) has been calculated to evaluate a possible causal relationship between the events/factors analysed. The hyper-geometric (Huygens and van Schooten, 1657; Pearson, 1899; Fisher, 1922; Gonin, 1936) distribution (HGD) has been used to test the one-sided significance of the causal relationship k . The study (design) bias has been controlled by IOI, the index of independence (Barukčić, 2019b) and IOU, the index of unfairness (Barukčić, 2019a). All the data were analysed using MS Excel (Microsoft Corporation, USA). The p values less than 0.05 were considered to indicate a statistically significant difference.

2.3. Axioms

2.3.1. Axiom I. Lex identitatis

In this context, we define axiom I as the expression

$$+ 1 = +1 \quad (2.86)$$

2.3.2. Axiom II. Lex contradictionis

In this context, axiom II or **lex contradictionis**, the negative of lex identitatis, or

$$+ 0 = +1 \quad (2.87)$$

and equally the most simple form of a contradiction formulated.

2.3.3. Axiom III. Lex negationis

$$\neg(0) \times 0 = 1 \quad (2.88)$$

where \neg denotes (logical (Boole, 1854) or natural) negation (Royce, 1917; Heinemann, 1943; Ayer, 1952; Hedwig, 1980; Kunen, 1987; Wedin, 1990; Koch, 1999; Horn, 1989; Speranza and Horn, 2010; Förster and Melamed, 2012; Newstadt, 2015). In this context, there is some evidence that $\neg(1) \times 1 = 0$. In other words, it is $(\neg(1) \times 1) \times (\neg(0) \times 0) = 1$

3. Results

Theorem 3.1 (STUDY DESIGN: EXCLUSION RELATIONSHIP). *A study which aims to investigate an exclusion relationship between events A_t and B_t should comply with the condition*

$$p(IOI(A, \underline{B})) \equiv Absolute\left(\left(\frac{A+B}{N}\right) - 1\right) = +0 \quad (3.1)$$

as far as possible. Otherwise, bias due to study design is pre-programmed and the danger is great that the conclusion drawn are not reliable enough.

Proof. The premise

$$\underbrace{+1 \equiv +1}_{\text{Premise}} \quad (3.2)$$

is true. Multiplying the equation 3.2 by the exclusion relationship (see equation 2.33), it is

$$\frac{b + \underline{A}}{N} \equiv \frac{c + \underline{B}}{N} \quad (3.3)$$

or

$$b + \underline{A} \equiv c + \underline{B} \quad (3.4)$$

Simplifying equation 3.4 it is

$$b + N - A \equiv c + \underline{B} \quad (3.5)$$

A design of a study which aims to assure an investigation of an exclusion relationship between events A_t and B_t should fully meet the condition

$$b \equiv c \quad (3.6)$$

Under these conditions, equation 3.5 simplifies as

$$N - A \equiv \underline{B} \quad (3.7)$$

and as

$$N \equiv A + \underline{B} \quad (3.8)$$

Rearranging equation 3.8, we obtain

$$+1 \equiv \frac{N}{N} \equiv \frac{A + \underline{B}}{N} \quad (3.9)$$

Simplifying equation 3.9, it is

$$+0 \equiv \frac{A + \underline{B}}{N} - 1 \quad (3.10)$$

or (see equation 2.65)

$$IOI(A, \underline{B}) \equiv \frac{A + \underline{B}}{N} - 1 \equiv +0 \quad (3.11)$$

Taking the absolute of equation 3.11, we obtain the index of independence (Barukčić, 2019b) as

$$p(IOI(A, \underline{B})) \equiv Absolute\left(\left(\frac{A + \underline{B}}{N}\right) - 1\right) = +0 \quad (3.12)$$

□

Theorem 3.2 (STUDY DESIGN: CONditio SINE QUA NON RELATIONSHIP). *A study which is planned to investigate a necessary condition relationship between events A_t and B_t should comply with the condition*

$$p(IOU(A, B)) \equiv Absolute\left(\left(\frac{A+B}{N}\right) - 1\right) = +0 \quad (3.13)$$

as much as possible. Otherwise, the danger is great that the data obtained by the study will not be reliable enough. Bias due to study design would be unavoidable.

Proof. The premise

$$\underbrace{+1 \equiv +1}_{\text{Premise}} \quad (3.14)$$

is true. Multiplying the equation 3.14 by the conditio sine qua non relationship (see equation 2.42), it is

$$\frac{d+A}{N} \equiv \frac{a+B}{N} \quad (3.15)$$

or

$$d+A \equiv a+B \quad (3.16)$$

Simplifying equation 3.16 it is

$$d+A \equiv a+N-B \quad (3.17)$$

A design of a study which aims to assure an investigation of a necessary condition (conditio sine qua non) relationship between events A_t and B_t should fully meet the condition

$$a \equiv d \quad (3.18)$$

Under these circumstances, equation 3.17 simplifies as

$$A \equiv N-B \quad (3.19)$$

and as

$$A+B \equiv N \quad (3.20)$$

Rearranging equation 3.20, we obtain

$$\frac{A+B}{N} \equiv \frac{N}{N} \equiv +1 \quad (3.21)$$

Simplifying equation 3.21, it is

$$\frac{A+B}{N} - 1 \equiv +0 \quad (3.22)$$

or (see equation 2.64)

$$IOU(A, B) \equiv \frac{A+B}{N} - 1 \equiv +0 \quad (3.23)$$

Taking the absolute of equation 3.23, we obtain the index of unfairness(Barukčić, 2019a) as

$$p(IOU(A, B)) \equiv Absolute\left(\left(\frac{A+B}{N}\right) - 1\right) = +0 \quad (3.24)$$

□

Theorem 3.3 (STUDY DESIGN: CONDITIO PER QUAM RELATIONSHIP). *A study which is planned to investigate a sufficient condition relationship between events A_t and B_t should comply with the condition*

$$p(IOU(A, B)) \equiv Absolute\left(\left(\frac{A+B}{N}\right) - 1\right) = +0 \quad (3.25)$$

as much as possible. Otherwise, the danger is great that the data obtained by the study will not be reliable enough. Bias due to study design would be unavoidable.

Proof. The premise

$$\underbrace{+1 \equiv +1}_{\text{Premise}} \quad (3.26)$$

is true. Multiplying the equation 3.26 by the conditio per quam relationship (see equation 2.46), it is

$$\frac{d+B}{N} \equiv \frac{a+A}{N} \quad (3.27)$$

or

$$d+B \equiv a+A \quad (3.28)$$

Simplifying equation 3.28 it is

$$d+B \equiv a+N-A \quad (3.29)$$

A design of a study which aims to assure an investigation of a sufficient condition (conditio per quam) relationship between events A_t and B_t should fully meet the condition

$$a \equiv d \quad (3.30)$$

Under these conditions, equation 3.29 simplifies as

$$A \equiv N-B \quad (3.31)$$

and as

$$A+B \equiv N \quad (3.32)$$

Rearranging equation 3.32, we obtain

$$\frac{A+B}{N} \equiv \frac{N}{N} \equiv +1 \quad (3.33)$$

Simplifying equation 3.33, it is

$$\frac{A+B}{N} - 1 \equiv +0 \quad (3.34)$$

or (see equation 2.64)

$$IOU(A, B) \equiv \frac{A+B}{N} - 1 \equiv +0 \quad (3.35)$$

Taking the absolute of equation 3.35, we obtain the index of unfairness (Barukčić, 2019a) as

$$p(IOU(A, B)) \equiv Absolute\left(\left(\frac{A+B}{N}\right) - 1\right) = +0 \quad (3.36)$$

□

Theorem 3.4 (STUDY DESIGN: NECESSARY AND SUFFICIENT CONDITION RELATIONSHIP). *A proof of the existence of a necessary and sufficient condition between events A_t and B_t is very helpful in order to be able to reliably identify causal relationships. A study which is planned to investigate a necessary and sufficient (causal relationship) condition relationship between events A_t and B_t should comply with the condition*

$$p(IOI(A, \underline{B})) \equiv \text{Absolute} \left(\left(\frac{A+B}{N} \right) - 1 \right) = +0 \quad (3.37)$$

as much as possible. Otherwise, the danger is great that the data obtained by the study will not be reliable enough. Bias due to study design would be unavoidable.

Proof. The premise

$$\underbrace{+1 \equiv +1}_{\text{Premise}} \quad (3.38)$$

is true. Under conditions of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship, a necessary condition (see equation 2.42) is equivalent with a sufficient condition (see equation 2.46). Equation 3.38 changes to

$$\frac{a + \underline{A}}{N} \equiv \frac{a + \underline{B}}{N} \quad (3.39)$$

or

$$a + \underline{A} \equiv a + \underline{B} \quad (3.40)$$

Simplifying equation 3.40 it is

$$N - A \equiv \underline{B} \quad (3.41)$$

or

$$N \equiv A + \underline{B} \quad (3.42)$$

Rearranging equation 3.42, we obtain

$$\frac{A + \underline{B}}{N} \equiv \frac{N}{N} \equiv +1 \quad (3.43)$$

Simplifying equation 3.43, it is

$$\frac{A + \underline{B}}{N} - 1 \equiv +0 \quad (3.44)$$

or (see equation 2.65)

$$IOI(A, \underline{B}) \equiv \frac{A + \underline{B}}{N} - 1 \equiv +0 \quad (3.45)$$

Taking the absolute of equation 3.45, we obtain the index of independence (Barukčić, 2019b) as

$$p(IOI(A, \underline{B})) \equiv \text{Absolute} \left(\left(\frac{A + \underline{B}}{N} \right) - 1 \right) = +0 \quad (3.46)$$

□

Theorem 3.5 (STUDY DESIGN: $B = C$). *A study that examines the necessary and sufficient condition relationship (i.e. causal relationship) should ensure conditions as far as possible and justifiable under which the following applies:*

$$b \equiv c \quad (3.47)$$

Proof. The premise

$$\underbrace{+1 \equiv +1}_{\text{Premise}} \quad (3.48)$$

is true. Multiplying the equation 3.48 by the expectation value of a sufficient condition see equation 2.46) it is,

$$E(A_t \rightarrow B_t) \equiv E(A_t \rightarrow B_t) \quad (3.49)$$

Under the conditions of this theorem, we are investigating experimental conditions where a sufficient condition is equivalent with a necessary condition (see equation 2.42). Under these circumstances, equation 3.49 becomes

$$E(A_t \leftarrow B_t) \equiv E(A_t \rightarrow B_t) \quad (3.50)$$

Equation 3.50 can be decomposed into single expectation values (see equation 2.42 and equation 2.46) as

$$a + d + b \equiv a + d + c \quad (3.51)$$

Simplifying equation 3.51, it is

$$b \equiv c \quad (3.52)$$

□

Remark 3.1. *In general, we might find ourselves compelled to calculate the following.*

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}((b=c) | c) &\equiv \frac{(b-c)^2}{c} + \\ &+ \frac{(c-c)^2}{c} \\ &\equiv \frac{(b-c)^2}{c} \end{aligned} \quad (3.53)$$

Theorem 3.6 (STUDY DESIGN: A = D). *An index of unfairness(Barukčić, 2019a) equivalent with*

$$p(\text{IOU}(A, B)) \equiv \text{Absolute} \left(\left(\frac{A+B}{N} \right) - 1 \right) = +0 \quad (3.54)$$

is grounded on the equation $a = d$.

Proof. The premise

$$\underbrace{+1 \equiv +1}_{\text{Premise}} \quad (3.55)$$

is true. Multiplying the equation 3.55 by the expectation value 'a' it is,

$$a \equiv a \quad (3.56)$$

Under the conditions of this theorem, we are investigating the effect of a design of a study which demands that $a = d$. Under these circumstances, equation 3.56 becomes

$$a \equiv d \quad (3.57)$$

Adding the expectation value 'b' to equation 3.57, we obtain

$$a + b \equiv d + b \quad (3.58)$$

which is equivalent with

$$A \equiv \underline{B} \quad (3.59)$$

and with

$$A \equiv N - B \quad (3.60)$$

Equation 3.60 can be rearranged as

$$A + B \equiv N \quad (3.61)$$

Rearranging equation 3.60, we obtain

$$\frac{A + B}{N} \equiv \frac{N}{N} \equiv +1 \quad (3.62)$$

Simplifying equation 3.62, it is

$$\frac{A + B}{N} - 1 \equiv +0 \quad (3.63)$$

or (see equation 2.64)

$$IOU(A, B) \equiv \frac{A + B}{N} - 1 \equiv +0 \quad (3.64)$$

Taking the absolute of equation 3.64, we obtain the index of unfairness(Barukčić, 2019a) as

$$p(IOU(A, B)) \equiv Absolute\left(\left(\frac{A + B}{N}\right) - 1\right) = +0 \quad (3.65)$$

□

Remark 3.2. *In general, we might calculate*

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\chi}^2_{Calculated}((a = d) | d) &\equiv \frac{(a - d)^2}{d} + \\ &+ 0 \\ &\equiv \frac{(a - d)^2}{d} \end{aligned} \quad (3.66)$$

Theorem 3.7 (STUDY DESIGN: CONTROL GROUP TRIALS). *Selecting an appropriate amount of patients for the control group is a very critical component of research of every case-control study. Furthermore, does the prevalence of the control group (CPR) adequately reflect the prevalence in the population? Many times, the study design of control group based trials, simply demand that*

$$p(IOU(A, B)) \equiv Absolute\left(\left(\frac{A + B}{N}\right) - 1\right) \equiv Absolute\left(\left(\frac{A + B}{N}\right) - 1\right) = p(IOI(A + \underline{B})) \quad (3.67)$$

Proof. The premise

$$\underbrace{+1 \equiv +1}_{Premise} \quad (3.68)$$

is true. Multiplying the equation 3.68 by the expectation value 'B' it is,

$$B \equiv B \quad (3.69)$$

Under many circumstances, the design of the study regularly requires examination conditions, which must ensure that $B = \underline{B}$ applies. Equation 3.69 becomes

$$B \equiv \underline{B} \quad (3.70)$$

Under these circumstances, the expectation value 'A' is added to equation 3.70. Equation 3.70 becomes

$$A + B \equiv A + \underline{B} \quad (3.71)$$

Dividing equation 3.71 by N, it is

$$\left(\frac{A+B}{N}\right) \equiv \left(\frac{A+\underline{B}}{N}\right) \quad (3.72)$$

or

$$\left(\frac{A+B}{N}\right) - 1 \equiv \left(\frac{A+\underline{B}}{N}\right) - 1 \quad (3.73)$$

Equation 3.73 changes according to equation 2.64 as

$$IOU(A, B) \equiv \left(\frac{A+\underline{B}}{N}\right) - 1 \quad (3.74)$$

According to equation 2.65, equation 3.74 becomes

$$IOU(A, B) \equiv IOI(A + \underline{B}) \quad (3.75)$$

Taking the absolute of equation 3.75, we obtain the equivalence of the index of unfairness (Barukčić, 2019a) and the index of independence (Barukčić, 2019b) as

$$p(IOU(A, B)) \equiv p(IOI(A + \underline{B})) \quad (3.76)$$

□

The requirement

$$p(IOU(A, B)) \equiv p(IOI(A + \underline{B})) \quad (3.77)$$

no longer seems to be sufficient to ensure bias reduced data. Rather, the key to success lies in the condition

$$p(IOU(A, B)) \equiv p(IOI(A + \underline{B})) \equiv +0 \quad (3.78)$$

which study design should ensure as much as possible.

Theorem 3.8 (STUDY DESIGN: PLACEBO CONTROLLED TRIALS AND IOU). *Bias is present everywhere in scientific research, and methods or measures to reduce the same are necessary. Single or double blinding is one of the various methods used to avoid bias in most placebo-controlled clinical trials (Chiodo et al., 2000). If the patient is unaware which treatment is applied, then the study is single blinded. If neither the patient nor the investigator knows which treatment is given, then the study is double blinded (e.g.*

drug administration versus placebo). Historically, the first control group has been used by James Lind (1716 – 1794), a Scottish physician, who conducted the first systematic experiment (Lind, 1757; Baron, 2009; Dunn, 1997) in 1747 to study the effect of citrus fruit on vitamin C deficiency, at that time better known as scurvy.

$$p(IOUS(A, B)) \equiv \text{Absolute} \left(\frac{A+B}{N} - 1 \right) \equiv \text{Absolute} \left(\frac{\underline{A}+B}{N} - 1 \right) \quad (3.79)$$

Proof. The premise

$$\underbrace{+1 \equiv +1}_{\text{Premise}} \quad (3.80)$$

is true. Multiplying the equation 3.80 by the expectation value 'A' it is,

$$A \equiv \underline{A} \quad (3.81)$$

The design of the study of placebo controlled trials regularly requires examination conditions, which must ensure that $A = \underline{A}$ applies. Under these circumstances, it is $A + A \equiv \underline{A} + A$ or $2 \times A \equiv N$ and at the end $A \equiv \frac{N}{2}$. Equation 3.81 becomes

$$A \equiv \underline{A} \quad (3.82)$$

The expectation value 'B' is added to equation 3.82. It is

$$A + B \equiv \underline{A} + B \quad (3.83)$$

Dividing equation 3.83 by N, it is

$$\frac{A+B}{N} \equiv \frac{\underline{A}+B}{N} \quad (3.84)$$

or

$$\frac{A+B}{N} - 1 \equiv \frac{\underline{A}+B}{N} - 1 \quad (3.85)$$

Under conditions of placebo controlled trials where $A = \underline{A}$ applies, the index of unfairness (Barukčić, 2019a) becomes (see equation 2.64)

$$p(IOUS(A, B)) \equiv \text{Absolute} \left(\frac{A+B}{N} - 1 \right) \equiv \text{Absolute} \left(\frac{\underline{A}+B}{N} - 1 \right) \quad (3.86)$$

□

Theorem 3.9 (STUDY DESIGN: PLACEBO CONTROLLED TRIALS AND IOI). Under conditions of placebo controlled trials where $A = \underline{A}$ applies, the index of independence (Barukčić, 2019b) becomes (see equation 2.65)

$$p(IOI(A, \underline{B})) \equiv \text{Absolute} \left(\frac{A+B}{N} - 1 \right) \equiv \text{Absolute} \left(\frac{\underline{A}+B}{N} - 1 \right) \quad (3.87)$$

Proof. The premise

$$\underbrace{+1 \equiv +1}_{\text{Premise}} \quad (3.88)$$

is true. Multiplying the equation 3.88 by the expectation value 'A' it is,

$$A \equiv A \quad (3.89)$$

The design of the study of placebo controlled trials regularly requires examination conditions, which must ensure that $A = \underline{A}$ applies. Under these circumstances, it is again $A + A \equiv \underline{A} + A$ or $2 \times A \equiv N$ and at the end $A \equiv \frac{N}{2}$. Equation 3.89 becomes

$$A \equiv \underline{A} \quad (3.90)$$

The expectation value 'B' is added to equation 3.90. It is

$$A + \underline{B} \equiv \underline{A} + \underline{B} \quad (3.91)$$

Dividing equation 3.91 by N, it is

$$\frac{A + \underline{B}}{N} \equiv \frac{\underline{A} + \underline{B}}{N} \quad (3.92)$$

or

$$\frac{A + \underline{B}}{N} - 1 \equiv \frac{\underline{A} + \underline{B}}{N} - 1 \quad (3.93)$$

Under conditions of placebo controlled trials where $A = \underline{A}$ applies, the index of independence (Barukčić, 2019b) becomes (see equation 2.65)

$$p(IOI(A, \underline{B})) \equiv Absolute\left(\frac{A + \underline{B}}{N} - 1\right) \equiv Absolute\left(\frac{\underline{A} + \underline{B}}{N} - 1\right) \quad (3.94)$$

□

Theorem 3.10 (Derivation of relative risk from axiom 1). *The relative risk can be derived from axiom 1 as*

$$RR_{nc}(A_t, B_t) \equiv \frac{a_t \times \underline{A}_t}{c_t \times \underline{A}_t} \quad (3.95)$$

Proof by direct proof. Axiom 1 or

$$+1 \equiv +1 \quad (3.96)$$

is correct. Multiplying by $\underline{A}_t > 0$, it is

$$\underline{A}_t \equiv \underline{A}_t \quad (3.97)$$

Dividing by $\underline{A}_t > 0$, it is

$$\frac{\underline{A}_t}{\underline{A}_t} \equiv \frac{\underline{A}_t}{\underline{A}_t} \quad (3.98)$$

Equation 3.97 is multiplied by ' a_t ' and becomes

$$\frac{a_t \times \underline{A}_t}{\underline{A}_t} \equiv \frac{a_t \times \underline{A}_t}{\underline{A}_t} \quad (3.99)$$

Equation 3.99 is divided by ' c_t ' and becomes

$$\underbrace{\frac{a_t \times \underline{A}_t}{c_t \times \underline{A}_t}}_{Relative\ risk} \equiv \frac{a_t \times \underline{A}_t}{c_t \times \underline{A}_t} \quad (3.100)$$

which is the definition of the relative risk RR_{nc} as

$$RR_{nc}(A_t, B_t) \equiv \frac{a_t \times \underline{A}_t}{c_t \times A_t} \quad (3.101)$$

From a formal point of view, the relative risk RR_{nc} can be derived from axiom 1 and is for these reasons mathematically correct but may still be of limited value. The definition of the relative risk includes the possibility to that $c_t = 0$ (see equation 3.99) which can be associated with logical problems. Today, the problem of the division by zero is not regarded as solved. \square

Theorem 3.11 (Derivation of odds ratio from axiom 1). *The odds can be derived from axiom 1 as*

$$OR(A_t, B_t) \equiv \frac{a_t \times d}{c_t \times b_t} \quad (3.102)$$

Proof by direct proof. Axiom 1 or

$$+ 1 \equiv +1 \quad (3.103)$$

is correct. Multiplying by ‘ a_t ’ and ‘ d_t ’, it is

$$a_t \times d_t \equiv a_t \times d_t \quad (3.104)$$

Dividing by ‘ b_t ’ and ‘ c_t ’, it is

$$\frac{a_t \times d_t}{b_t \times c_t} \equiv \frac{a_t \times d_t}{b_t \times c_t} \quad (3.105)$$

From a formal mathematical point of view, odds ratio can be derived from axiom 1 and is on a preliminary basis correct. It is

$$OR(A_t, B_t) \equiv \frac{a_t \times d_t}{b_t \times c_t} \quad (3.106)$$

However, the definition of odds ratio includes the possibility to that $b_t = 0$ and/or $c_t = 0$ which can be associated with logical problems. Today, the division by zero is not accepted as solved. \square

Theorem 3.12 (THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN RELATIVE RISK (RR) AND INDEX OF RELATIONSHIP (IOR)). *The relationship between relative risk (RR_{nc}) and index of relationship (IOR) is determined by the equation*

$$RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc} \equiv \left(\frac{(Not A_t) \times B_t}{N \times c_t} \right) \times (IOR(A_t, B_t) + 1) \quad (3.107)$$

Proof. The relative risk RR_{nc} is defined as

$$RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc} \equiv \frac{a_t \times (Not A_t)}{c_t \times A_t} \quad (3.108)$$

Rearranging, it is

$$\frac{(RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc}) \times c_t \times A_t}{(Not A_t)} \equiv a_t \quad (3.109)$$

Rearranging further, we obtain

$$\frac{N \times (RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc}) \times c_t \times A_t}{(NotA_t) \times A_t \times B_t} \equiv \frac{N \times a_t}{A_t \times B_t} \quad (3.110)$$

It follows that

$$\left(\frac{N \times (RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc}) \times c_t \times A_t}{(NotA_t) \times A_t \times B_t} \right) - 1 \equiv \left(\frac{N \times a_t}{A_t \times B_t} \right) - 1 \quad (3.111)$$

or that

$$\left(\frac{N \times (RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc}) \times c_t \times A_t}{(NotA_t) \times B_t \times A_t} \right) - 1 \equiv IOR(A_t, B_t) \quad (3.112)$$

Rearranging equation before, we obtain

$$\left(\frac{N \times (RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc}) \times c_t}{(NotA_t) \times B_t} \right) \equiv IOR(A_t, B_t) + 1 \quad (3.113)$$

In general, the relative risk (RR) forces us to accept the following relationship.

$$RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc} \equiv \left(\frac{(NotA_t) \times B_t}{N \times c_t} \right) \times (IOR(A_t, B_t) + 1) \quad (3.114)$$

□

Theorem 3.13 (THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN RELATIVE RISK (RR) AND ODDS RATIO (OR)). *The relationship between relative risk (RR_{nc}) and odds ratio (OR) is determined by the equation*

$$RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc} \equiv \left(\frac{(NotA_t) \times b_t}{A_t \times d_t} \right) \times OR(A_t, B_t) \quad (3.115)$$

Proof. The relative risk RR_{nc} is defined as

$$RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc} \equiv \frac{a_t \times (NotA_t)}{c_t \times A_t} \quad (3.116)$$

Rearranging, it is

$$\frac{(RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc}) \times c_t \times A_t}{(NotA_t)} \equiv a_t \quad (3.117)$$

Rearranging further, we obtain

$$\frac{(RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc}) \times c_t \times A_t \times d_t}{(NotA_t) \times b_t \times c_t} \equiv \frac{a_t \times d_t}{b_t \times c_t} \quad (3.118)$$

Equation before simplifies as

$$\frac{(RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc}) \times A_t \times d_t}{(NotA_t) \times b_t} \equiv OR(A_t, B_t) \quad (3.119)$$

In point of fact, the relative risk (RR) forces us to accept the following relationship.

$$RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc} \equiv \left(\frac{(NotA_t) \times b_t}{A_t \times d_t} \right) \times OR(A_t, B_t) \quad (3.120)$$

□

Theorem 3.14 (THE RELATIVE RISK IS LOGICALLY INCONSISTENT AND REFUTED). *Relative risk is mathematically false and cognitively invaluable because the same is grounded on the logical contradiction that*

$$+0 \equiv +1 \quad (3.121)$$

Proof by counter-example. The premise

$$\underbrace{+1 \equiv +1}_{\text{Premise}} \quad (3.122)$$

is true. From such a premise and in the absence of errors, it is not allowed to derive a logical contradiction. Multiplying the equation 3.122 by the relative risk, $RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc} \equiv \frac{a_t \times \underline{A}_t}{c_t \times A_t}$ (see equation 2.67), it is

$$RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc} \equiv RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc} \quad (3.123)$$

or

$$RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc} \equiv \frac{a_t \times \underline{A}_t}{c_t \times A_t} \quad (3.124)$$

Rearranging equation 3.124, we obtain

$$\frac{(RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc}) \times c_t \times A_t}{\underline{A}_t} \equiv a_t \quad (3.125)$$

where A_t , \underline{A}_t , c_t and a_t might denote the expectation values. Adding the expectation value \underline{B}_t to equation 3.125, it is

$$\underline{B}_t + \frac{(RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc}) \times c_t \times A_t}{\underline{A}_t} \equiv a_t + \underline{B}_t \quad (3.126)$$

Equation 3.126 is the way how the relative risk defines the necessary condition. In general, we have to accept that

$$\underline{B}_t + \frac{(RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc}) \times c_t \times A_t}{\underline{A}_t} \equiv a_t + \underline{B}_t \equiv E(A_t \leftarrow B_t) \quad (3.127)$$

where $E(A_t \leftarrow B_t)$ is the expectation value of the necessary condition (see equation 2.42). By definition, the necessary condition requires that $c_t = 0$. We plug this value into equation 3.127 for c_t and get

$$\underline{B}_t + \frac{(RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc}) \times 0 \times A_t}{\underline{A}_t} \equiv a_t + \underline{B}_t \quad (3.128)$$

or

$$\underline{B}_t \equiv a_t + \underline{B}_t \quad (3.129)$$

Finally, the relative risk defines the necessary condition by the fact that $a_t = 0$.

$$+0 \equiv a_t \quad (3.130)$$

However, it is essential to note that the necessary condition is also given for values of $a_t > +0$, for example if $a_t = 1$. Under these conditions, the relative risk demand us to accept that

$$+0 \equiv +1 \quad (3.131)$$

Without further ado, it is possible to derive a **logical contradiction** from the relative risk which is not possible to accept. Matters seem clear enough, as much as they can be. In these circumstances, there is some evidence that the relative risk is logically inconsistent and refuted.

□

Theorem 3.15 (The relative risk is not refuted). *In general, we want to be in a position to face all eventualities as we continue to investigate the logical consistency of relative risk. Therefore, we need to re-examine the relative risk in full knowledge of all detailed facts from another, different point of view. There may be circumstances under which the relative risk $RR_{nc}(A_t, B_t)$ defined as*

$$RR_{nc}(A_t, B_t) \equiv \frac{a_t \times \underline{A}_t}{c_t \times A_t} \quad (3.132)$$

is logically consistent.

Proof by direct proof. The relative risk for values $A_t, \underline{A}_t > 0$ has been derived from axiom 1 as (see equation 3.101)

$$RR_{nc}(A_t, B_t) \equiv \frac{a_t \times \underline{A}_t}{c_t \times A_t} \quad (3.133)$$

Equation 3.133 demands under any circumstances, including $c=0$, that

$$\left(\frac{a_t \times \underline{A}_t}{c_t \times A_t} \right) \equiv \left(\frac{a_t \times \underline{A}_t}{c_t \times A_t} \right) \quad (3.134)$$

Solving for 'a', it is

$$\left(\frac{a_t \times \underline{A}_t}{c_t \times A_t} \right) \times \left(\frac{c_t \times A_t}{\underline{A}_t} \right) \equiv \left(\frac{a_t \times \underline{A}_t}{c_t \times A_t} \right) \times \left(\frac{c_t \times A_t}{\underline{A}_t} \right) \quad (3.135)$$

In order to find out the relationship between the necessary condition and the relative risk, we add \underline{B}_t to equation 3.135. It is

$$\left(\frac{a_t \times \underline{A}_t}{c_t \times A_t} \right) \times \left(\frac{c_t \times A_t}{\underline{A}_t} \right) + \underline{B}_t \equiv \left(\frac{a_t \times \underline{A}_t}{c_t \times A_t} \right) \times \left(\frac{c_t \times A_t}{\underline{A}_t} \right) + \underline{B}_t \equiv E(A_t \leftarrow B_t) \quad (3.136)$$

As known, it is $A_t, \underline{A}_t > 0$. Therefore, equation 3.136 can be simplified as

$$\left(\frac{a_t \times c_t}{c_t} \right) + \underline{B}_t \equiv \left(\frac{a_t \times c_t}{c_t} \right) + \underline{B}_t \equiv E(A_t \leftarrow B_t) \quad (3.137)$$

For any case $c_t > 0$, there would be no logical contradiction between the relative risk and the necessary condition. However, the necessary condition itself is defined especially by the case that $c_t = 0$. Under these circumstances, we obtain

$$\left(\frac{a_t \times 0}{0} \right) + \underline{B}_t \equiv \left(\frac{a_t \times 0}{0} \right) + \underline{B}_t \equiv E(A_t \leftarrow B_t) \quad (3.138)$$

Logically, the relative risk can only survive if we accept that $\frac{0}{0} \equiv +1$. Only under these conditions, we would obtain a logically consistent result as,

$$(a_t \times 1) + \underline{B}_t \equiv (a_t \times 1) + \underline{B}_t \equiv E(A_t \leftarrow B_t) \quad (3.139)$$

Even if there is increasing evidence (Barukčić and Barukčić, 2016; Barukčić, 2018, 2019d, 2020e; Barukčić and Ufuoma, 2020b) that $\frac{0}{0} \equiv +1$, the division by zero cannot be regarded as generally accepted. Therefore, we are left with the following dilemma. **Either** give up classical logic and accept the relative risk, **or** accept classic logic and dismiss the validity of the relative risk (as long as $\frac{0}{0} \equiv +1$ is not generally accepted). The first alternative is not possible, the second alternative appears to be mind threatening and terrible. In general, we cannot rely on this measure of relationship to a necessary extent. Having said this, any further use of this measure of relationship is dangerous, irresponsible and should be stopped immediately or at least reduced as much as possible. \square

Theorem 3.16 (ODDS RATIO (OR) IS POTENTIALLY LOGICALLY INCONSISTENT). *Odds ratio is not for sure logically consistent.*

Proof by direct proof. The premise

$$\underbrace{+1 \equiv +1}_{\text{Premise}} \quad (3.140)$$

is true. Again, even in this case, from such a premise and in the absence of errors, it is not allowed to derive a logical contradiction. Multiplying the equation 3.122 by Odds ratio, $OR(A_t, B_t) \equiv \frac{a_t \times d_t}{b_t \times c_t}$ (see equation 2.85), it is

$$OR(A_t, B_t) \equiv OR(A_t, B_t) \quad (3.141)$$

or

$$\left(\frac{a_t \times d_t}{b_t \times c_t} \right) \equiv a_t \times \left(\frac{d_t}{b_t \times c_t} \right) \quad (3.142)$$

Rearranging equation 3.142, it is

$$\left(\frac{a_t \times d_t}{b_t \times c_t} \right) \times \left(\frac{b_t \times c_t}{d_t} \right) \equiv a_t \times \left(\frac{d_t}{b_t \times c_t} \right) \times \left(\frac{b_t \times c_t}{d_t} \right) \quad (3.143)$$

where a_t , \underline{B}_t , b_t , c_t and d_t might denote the expectation values. Adding the expectation value \underline{B}_t to equation 3.143, it is

$$\underline{B}_t + \left(\frac{a_t \times d_t}{b_t \times c_t} \right) \times \left(\frac{b_t \times c_t}{d_t} \right) \equiv a_t \times \left(\frac{d_t}{b_t \times c_t} \right) \times \left(\frac{b_t \times c_t}{d_t} \right) + \underline{B}_t \quad (3.144)$$

Equation 3.144 is the definition of the necessary condition by odds ratio and simplifies as

$$\underline{B}_t + \left(\frac{a_t \times d_t}{b_t \times c_t} \right) \times \left(\frac{b_t \times c_t}{d_t} \right) \equiv a_t \times \left(\frac{d_t}{b_t \times c_t} \right) \times \left(\frac{b_t \times c_t}{d_t} \right) + \underline{B}_t \equiv E(A_t \leftarrow B_t) \quad (3.145)$$

where $E(A_t \leftarrow B_t)$ is the expectation value of the necessary condition (see equation 2.42). Equation 3.145 is the way in which odds ratio defines the necessary condition. However, and by definition, the necessary condition requires to that $c_t = 0$. Under these circumstance's equation 3.145 becomes

$$\underline{B}_t + \left(\frac{a_t \times d_t}{b_t \times 0} \right) \times \left(\frac{b_t \times 0}{d_t} \right) \equiv a_t \times \left(\frac{d_t}{b_t \times 0} \right) \times \left(\frac{b_t \times 0}{d_t} \right) + \underline{B}_t \equiv E(A_t \leftarrow B_t) \quad (3.146)$$

Under conditions of a necessary condition, odds ratio demands that

$$\underline{B}_t + \frac{a_t \times 0}{0} \equiv \underline{B}_t + \frac{a_t \times 0}{0} \equiv E(A_t \leftarrow B_t) \quad (3.147)$$

which would be logically consistent only under conditions where $\frac{0}{0} \equiv +1$ otherwise not. Today we are not enabled to deal with the term $\frac{a_t \times 0}{0}$. Odds' ratio is not for sure logically consistent. Under these conditions, any further use of odds ratio would be not right and should be omitted immediately. \square

4. Discussion

A study should provide us with data which enable us to answer a specific research question for 'sure'. Nevertheless, it makes little sense to investigate the whole population of interest. Under normal circumstances, a sample is drawn from the population, investigated and the results from this specific sample are used to generalize for the whole population. Furthermore, it is self-evident that the sample drawn from a population should be properly selected and highly representative (Röhrig et al., 2009) of the study population. No wonder that one of the main aspects of any study design of a study is to laid down, carefully, the fundamental points for fulfilling the objectives of a study long before the study itself has been completed. However, a distinction must be made between a study which aims to investigate causal relationships between events and a study which is designed primarily to investigate conditions or risk factors et cetera because this would determine the type and the extent of the data to be recorded. In case of causal relationship investigations, it should be a priority of a study design to strive for a $p(\text{IOI}) = 0$. Under circumstance where single conditions or risk factors are investigated, the objective of the design of a study should be to assure as much as possible a $p(\text{IOU}) = 0$. Unfortunately, studies with certain features (Sutton et al., 2000) are more likely to be published, or published even more rapidly, than studies without certain characteristics. By time, a resulting bias will accumulate and has the potential to invalidate the conclusions drawn, especially if erroneous studies are frequently cited. Under our today's valid mathematical rules, The logical consistency of the relative risk and the odds ratio is based on the logical need that $\frac{0}{0} \equiv +1$ (see equation 3.138 and equation 3.147). Today, this pure logical requirement excludes the possibility for us to accept that the relative risk and the odds ratio are logically consistent. However, and in other factual circumstances (assumed that $\frac{0}{0} \equiv +1$ is correct), the relative risk and the odds ratio were fully logically consistent. Unfortunately, investigators who use the relative risk or the odds ratio today will not know for sure what is what and in which they will be involved.

5. Conclusion

So, viewed against this backdrop, our results are solid and gratifying. The relative risk and the odds' ratio are not for sure logically consistent and therefore refuted.

Acknowledgments

No funding or any financial support by a third party was received.

6. Patient consent for publication

Not required.

Conflict of interest statement

No conflict of interest to declare.

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I was born October, 1st 1961 in Novo Selo, Bosnia and Herzegovina, former Yugoslavia. I am of Croatian origin. From 1982-1989 C.E., I studied human medicine at the University of Hamburg, Germany. Meanwhile, I am working as a specialist of internal medicine. My basic field of research since my high school days at the Wirtschaftsgymnasium Bruchsal, Baden Württemberg, Germany is the mathematization of the relationship between a cause and an effect valid without any restriction under any circumstances including the conditions of classical logic, probability theory, quantum mechanics, special and general theory of relativity, human medicine et cetera. I endeavour to investigate positions of quantum mechanics, relativity theory, mathematics et cetera, only insofar as these positions put into question or endanger **the general validity of the principle of causality**.

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